

FINANCIAL LITERACY AND PURCHASE SELF - CONTROL AS DETERMINANTS OF SAVING BEHAVIOR AMONG PERSONNEL IN A COMMUNITY COLLEGE IN MISAMIS ORIENTAL

Recie M. Salubo and Cyril C. Chavez

*Business Administration, Lourdes College, Inc., Cagayan de Oro City,
Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15731218>

ABSTRACT

Financial literacy and purchase self-control play a crucial role in shaping saving behavior, particularly among personnel in educational institutions. This study determined the relationship between financial literacy and purchase self-control on the saving behavior among community college personnel in Misamis Oriental using a quantitative correlational research design. Data were gathered from 141 participants through a structured survey questionnaire, employing validated instruments with high reliability. Descriptive and Inferential Statistics (regression) were used to analyze the data. Results reveal that participants generally rated their purchase self-control, saving behavior, and financial literacy as generally high. Findings further show that both financial literacy and purchase self-control influence saving behavior, with financial literacy emerging as the stronger predictor. Participants with higher financial literacy demonstrate stronger budgeting skills, better investment knowledge, and a greater ability to plan for long-term financial security. Similarly, those with greater purchase self-control exhibit disciplined spending habits, effectively managing impulsive buying and prioritizing savings. The study highlights the necessity of structured financial literacy programs and behavioral self-control strategies to enhance financial well-being among employees.

Keywords: *Financial literacy, Purchase self-control, Saving behavior*

INTRODUCTION

Globalization and increasing economic challenges have highlighted the importance of financial literacy and education in policy discussions Kaiser & Lusardi, (2024). Understanding financial concepts is crucial in a complex financial landscape, especially amid rising inflation. Desello & Agner (2024). emphasizes that financial literacy promotes financial inclusion, as individuals with higher financial knowledge are more likely to utilize formal financial services. However, despite these benefits, many public sector employees continue to face financial difficulties, reflected in the sector's low growth rates in recent years.

Research also suggests a strong link between financial literacy and saving behavior According to Pamungkas (2022) while studies have examined financial literacy and self-control among public sector employees, limited research focuses specifically on community college personnel, particularly in Misamis Oriental. Given the financial challenges faced by employees in this sector, it is essential to explore how financial literacy and self-control impact their saving habits. Encio et. al. (2022) highlight the significance of financial education in fostering economic stability. Tailored financial education programs can improve financial decision-making and enhance money management skills. In the context of community college employees, interventions such as workplace financial training could strengthen their budgeting and savings practices. A strong financial literacy foundation helps individuals make informed financial decisions, while self-control in spending reduces impulsive purchases and promotes savings.

Financial mismanagement often results from a lack of experience and awareness, leading to financial stress and poor savings performance. Research indicates that financial capability, combined with emotional intelligence regarding money, plays a vital role in wealth management Strömbäck et al., (2020). Given these issues, this study aimed to examine the relationship between financial literacy, self-control, and saving behavior among community college personnel in Misamis Oriental. Understanding these factors can help develop policies and programs to enhance financial security and well-being among employees in similar settings. According to Faramida et. al. (2023) examined how financial literacy and self-control affect saving behavior among university students, highlighting the importance of these factors in financial decision-making. Their study emphasizes that both cognitive and behavioral aspects significantly shape saving patterns among young adults. Supporting this, Bingil et al. (2024) found that financial knowledge significantly enhances financial well-being and responsible money management. Their research aligns with the idea that financial literacy fosters saving behavior and also highlights the role of impulsivity and behavioral control key aspects of purchase self-control further reinforcing their impact on financial decisions and savings.

According to Bai (2023). Mental budgeting is also crucial to financial health. Individuals and households utilize cognitive operations to arrange and control their finances. It entails budgeting for several expenditure categories and mentally dividing the monies. Mental budgeting aids in spending tracking, goal setting, and financial decision-making. The COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped individual saving behaviors in response to heightened

economic uncertainty. Gunawan et al. (2022) examined the financial behavior of individuals in Medan, Indonesia, highlighting notable changes in saving habits during the crisis. The study asserts that during periods of economic uncertainty, particularly in crisis conditions, individuals are more likely to initiate "burst saving" strategies to build emergency funds. This response underscores the influence of situational factors on saving behavior and aligns with the broader view that external pressures can motivate prudent financial actions. Jiang (2023) emphasized that households with higher financial literacy exhibited better financial planning and saving behavior. He further noted that saving is not solely a function of knowledge, but also influenced by attitudes and habits. Nguyen & Doan (2020) conducted a study in Vietnam that revealed a significant positive correlation between financial literacy and saving behavior. Their findings demonstrated that individuals with higher financial knowledge were more likely to adopt saving practices and manage their finances effectively.

Research Questions

This study examined the relationship between self-control factors, financial literacy skills, and saving behavior among municipal college personnel in Misamis Oriental. Specifically, it explored the influence of self-control and financial literacy on the saving habits of personnel.

1. What is the participants' assessment of their purchase self-control?
2. What is the participants' assessment of their financial Literacy?
3. What is the participants' assessment of their saving behavior?
4. Do the participants' purchase self-control and financial Literacy influence their saving behavior?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive correlational research design to examine the influence of purchase self-control and financial literacy on the saving behavior of community college personnel in Misamis Oriental, following established approaches to studying natural relationships among variables. A total of 218 active employees were selected through simple random sampling, with a required sample size of 141 determined using a standard sampling formula. A questionnaire was used to measure purchase self-control, financial literacy, and saving behavior. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency, percentage, and mean, were utilized to evaluate the respondents' levels of financial literacy, purchase self-control, and saving behavior. A regression analysis was conducted to determine the significant influence of financial literacy and purchase self-control on saving behavior.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals the high evaluation of purchase self-control aligns with broader research on self-regulation and personal financial management. This suggests that participants

generally feel capable of controlling their purchasing decisions in a way that likely supports their financial well-being.

The participants generally exhibited a high level of purchase self-control with an overall mean of 3.91 (SD = 0.62). The most highly rated indicator was “avoiding credit for non-essential purchases” (M = 4.04), which reflects their ability to manage debt prudently. On the other hand, items like “saving money instead of spending on non-essential desires” received slightly lower scores, suggesting room for improvement in impulse control. Participants generally rated their purchase self-control as generally high. The strongest area was their commitment to avoiding unnecessary credit use, as they prioritize essential purchases over-borrowing. This reflects a responsible approach to financial management and reinforces their dedication to maintaining financial stability. On the other hand, the weakest area was careful purchase planning and avoiding impulsive spending. While still rated high, this suggests that some individuals may struggle with impulse control or occasional unplanned spending.

This finding aligns with Bai (2023), who emphasized that individuals with stronger purchase control are more successful in achieving financial goals. The consistent high ratings across all items reflect that participants possess a mindful approach to spending, which supports positive saving behavior. However, slight variability indicates that targeted financial coaching may further enhance self-regulation.

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participant’s Assessment of their Purchase Self-control

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
3.51-4.50	High	94	66.67
2.51-3.50	Moderate	28	19.86
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.42
1.00-1.50	Very Low	1	0.71
	Total	141	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.91	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.62	

Table 2 reveals the high evaluation of financial literacy among participants aligns with broader research emphasizing the importance of financial education in fostering responsible money management behaviors. The necessity of current financial literacy programs becomes evident since they help people understand methods to deal with financial obstacles more effectively Nguyen & Doan (2020).

Participants reported a high level of financial literacy, with an overall mean of 3.78 (SD = 0.66). The highest-rated item was “assessing financial knowledge and applying new

strategies” (M = 3.89), suggesting a proactive attitude toward financial learning. Meanwhile, creating annual financial plans received a relatively lower score, hinting at gaps in long-term planning.

Participants rated their financial literacy as generally high. The strongest area was their commitment to regularly assessing their financial knowledge and applying new strategies to improve savings. This reflects a proactive approach to financial management and a dedication to continuous improvement. However, the weakest area was creating a yearly financial plan for future needs like emergencies or major purchases.

This supports Bai (2023) who assert that ongoing financial education is crucial in cultivating sustainable saving habits. The data suggest that while participants are confident in budgeting and saving, structured support in long-term planning could be beneficial.

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the participant’s assessment of their financial literacy

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	11	7.80
3.51-4.50	High	83	58.87
2.51-3.50	Moderate	28	19.86
1.51-2.50	Low	45	1.42
1.00-1.50	Very Low	2	1.42
	Total	141	100.0
	Overall Mean	3.78	
	Interpretation	High	
	SD	0.66	

Table 3 presents the high evaluation of saving behavior aligns with broader research on financial discipline and personal financial management. This suggests that participants generally feel capable of managing their savings effectively in a way that supports their long-term financial well-being.

The participants’ saving behavior was also rated high, with an overall mean of 3.98 (SD = 0.62). The strongest behavior was “seeking income opportunities to increase savings” (M = 4.11), reflecting a proactive financial mindset. In contrast, following a strict monthly budget had a slightly lower score, suggesting a need for greater consistency.

Participants rated their saving habits as generally high. The strongest area was their effort to increase savings by seeking additional income opportunities, such as side jobs or extra work. This reflects a proactive approach to financial security and a strong commitment to building their savings. Additionally, they prioritize setting aside unexpected income, such as bonuses or gifts, demonstrating financial foresight and responsibility. On the other

hand, the weakest areas were following a monthly budget and saving for specific financial targets, such as buying a car or paying for education. While still considered strong habits, this suggests that some individuals may struggle with consistency in budgeting or setting clear financial goals.

These findings align Encio et. al.(2022), who highlight that saving behavior is enhanced by both income strategies and budgeting discipline. The data indicate a strong inclination toward saving but reveal that structured financial tracking tools might support further improvements.

Table 3:
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the participant's assessment of their saving behavior

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	27	19.15
3.51-4.50	High	85	60.28
2.51-3.50	Moderate	27	19.15
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.42
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0
Total		141	100.0
Overall Mean		3.98	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.62	

Table 4
Regression Analysis: Influence of Financial Literacy and Purchase Self-Control on Saving Behavior

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.951	.207		4.595	.000
Purchase Control	.158	.072	.158	2.20*	.030
Financial Literacy	.639	.067	.686	9.56**	.000
Model Summary					
R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F	P	
.806 ^a	.649	.644	127.502*	.000	

*Significance at 0.05 level

** Significance at 0.01 level

Ho1. The participants purchase self-control does not influence their saving behavior.

Ho2. The participants' financial literacy does not influence their saving behavior.

The regression model explains 64.9 percent of the variability in participants' saving behavior ($R^2 = 0.649$), indicating that financial literacy and purchase self-control play substantial roles in shaping saving patterns. However, 35.1 percent of the variability remains unexplained, suggesting that other factors such as income levels, spending habits, and psychological influences may also impact saving behavior Faramida et. al. (2023)

The regression analysis demonstrates the influence of Purchase self-control and financial literacy on the participants saving behavior leading to the rejection of the both (Ho1 and Ho2) null hypothesis: The model explains a substantial proportion of the variance ($R^2 = 0.649$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.644$ $F=127.502$, $p=0.000$), indicating that this predictor collectively Accounting for 64.9% of the variability participants saving behavior. This suggest that 35.1% of the variability remains unexplained by the predictors in this model. Suggesting that other factors such as income level, spending habits, and psychological influences may also impact saving behavior Faramida et. al. (2023)

Among the predictors Financial Literacy emerges as the most significant determinant (Beta=.686, $p<0.001$). This suggests that for one-unit increase in financial literacy there is .639 units increase on saving behavior. This suggest that individuals with greater financial knowledge engage in better financial management, including disciplined saving and informed design making (Jiang (2023) The strong influence of financial literacy can be attributed to its role in equipping individuals with the necessary skills to the budget effectively assess financial risks, and set long-term financial goals. People with the higher financial literacy tend to make more informed decisions about spending, investing, and saving, leading to the better financial security & wealth accumulation over time. Furthermore, financial literacy Fosters a proactive approach to money management, reducing financial stress and encouraging consistent saving habits.

The second predictor is purchase self-control with Beta at .686 and P value at 0.030. This suggests that for one-unit increase in purchase self-control there is 0.158 units increase on saving behavior. This suggest that participants are more conscious of the products they purchase. They are more inclined to saving than spending. According to the study of Bingil et al. (2024), pointed that self-control impacts financial income and expenditures that individuals with greater self-control are more likely to engage in goal-oriented financial behaviors, such as setting aside money for future needs.

Regression analysis confirms that both purchase self-control and financial literacy significantly influence saving behavior, with financial literacy emerging as the stronger predictor. Individuals with higher financial literacy are more likely to engage in disciplined

saving, effective budgeting, and informed financial decision-making, highlighting the crucial role of financial education in fostering sound money management Bai (2023).

While Purchase self-control helps individuals resist impulsive spending and maintain disciplined financial habits, its influence on saving behavior is weaker compared to financial literacy. This further indicates that improving financial knowledge is essential for sustainable saving habits, as self-control alone may not be sufficient to drive significant financial improvements Strömbäck (2020).

The findings also indicate that while financial literacy and self-control are key determinants of saving behavior, other factors such as income levels, spending habits, and psychological influences also play a role. Therefore, financial education initiatives should be complemented by behavioral strategies such as goal-setting, mindful spending and delayed gratification techniques to enhance overall financial well-being. Strengthening financial literacy through targeted programs can empower individuals to make informed financial decisions, build sustainable saving habits, and achieve long-term financial security, while promoting self-discipline further enhances financial resilience.

Conclusions

This study validates key theoretical concepts, aligning with Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior and Shefrin and Thaler's Behavioral Life-Cycle Hypothesis. Findings confirm that financial knowledge and self-control significantly influence financial decision-making and saving behavior. While both factors play a role, financial literacy emerges as the stronger predictor of saving behavior. The results highlight the need for targeted financial education programs, as financial knowledge found more effective in guiding financial decisions than self-control in specific contexts, such as online shopping. Education initiatives should not only teach financial principles but also provide practical applications to help individuals integrate knowledge into real-life financial decisions.

Financial education organizations should incorporate experiential learning to enhance saving behavior, goal setting, and expenditure monitoring. The study contributes valuable empirical insights into factors influencing saving behavior, reinforcing the importance of structured financial literacy programs in improving financial discipline and long-term economic well-being.

Recommendations

A series of recommendations derived from the study results and findings are as follows:

1. Administration

- 1.1 may organize structured financial literacy training, including budgeting lessons, investment principles, and long-term planning methods.
- 1.2 may conduct workshops to present financial literacy basics and maintain an environment where learning happens continuously.

2. Hr Extension

2.1 may provide guidance on how employees can effectively manage their money how to save and also manage expenses efficiently.

2.2 Through financial counseling services, Hr may assist workers seeking help with debt management, investment, and saving decisions.

3. Employees

3.1 Employees may participate in goal-setting exercises and use behavioral tracking to improve purchasing self-control.

4. Future Researchers

4.1 The study may investigate additional saving behavior determinants, including monetary steadiness, financial technology platforms, and societal effects.

4.2 The researchers must analyze saving habits between various employment markets to identify universal patterns.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher followed data protocols and ethical standards in conducting this study, where all rights and integrity of participants are guaranteed throughout the process. Before the data gathering, the researcher obtained the clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee. Subsequently, the researcher sought permission from all the concerned parties involved in the study. The participants were given an informed consent form stating the purpose of the study, the rights of the participants, and confidentiality. The researcher also assured the participants that their participation was purely voluntary with the right to leave or refuse to answer any questions.

This procedure follows the respect for persons principle in the Belmont Report by emphasizing the requirement of obtaining informed consent and safeguarding the participants' autonomy Amdor & Banker, (2020). The researcher also ensured that no undue risks, stressors, or discomforts would be caused to the participants. The researcher also avoided any conflict of interest that could compromise the integrity of the study by following the Belmont principle of justice, which stipulates that all participants must receive fair and unbiased treatment Amdor & Banker, (2020). All through the research process, transparency and professionalism were maintained.

Moreover, the researcher ensured that data were kept in a safe location and that identifying information was not provided as such but rather was coded for anonymity. Survey questionnaires were also kept in a safe location, and encrypted data storage methods were used to keep sensitive information secure. After the research, all the data collected were destroyed in a manner adhering to the Belmont principle, which emphasizes doing maximum good and causing minimum harm Amdor & Banker, (2020).

Acknowledgments

The Researcher are deeply grateful to everyone who supported me throughout the journey of completing this thesis. To my thesis advisor, Cyril C. Chavez, whose invaluable

guidance, encouragement, and constructive critiques have significantly influenced this research. Your insights were essential to its development.

To the members of my thesis committee Anthony L. Dagang, Rhandy N. Oyao, Miguela B. Napiere, and Judith C. Chavez for their expertise, suggestions, and the critical feedback that enhanced the quality of my work. To the faculty and staff at Lourdes College for providing the necessary resources and support throughout the research process. A special thank you to my family, especially my two sons, whose constant love, encouragement, and belief in me have been a continual source of strength. I am also thankful for my friends, Crazelle, Elvie, and others, for their emotional support, motivation, and for sharing in both the challenges and triumphs I faced.

Lastly, the researcher appreciates the participants and contributors to this study, whose involvement was crucial to its completion. To everyone who played a role, either directly or indirectly, in the success of this thesis, I am deeply appreciate

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